

BEHAVIOUR OF ARAMID/EPOXY WOUNDED TUBES UNDER UNIAXIAL AND BIAxIAL LOADING

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ABSTRACT

To know how to dimension industrial composite structures, we study the prevision mechanical behaviour under uniaxial and biaxial loads, determined from tests on the elementary sheet.

INTRODUCTION

To adjust the performances (weight and mechanical behaviour) of tubular structures in composite materials, realized by filament winding process, number and ply orientation are determined in accordance with imposed sollicitations.

The studied laminate is an Aramid (49) fiber with epoxide resin.

From the experimental study of unidirectional tube, determining the elementary ply characteristics, we will try to foresee the complex structures behaviour under different sollicitations.

EXPERIMENTS

a- Test tubes :

Three types of winding tubes are studied :

-UD: unidirectional, composed by four 90° plies.

-BD: angle-ply, composed with two $\pm 55^\circ$ plies.

-MD: multi-ply, combining the two precedent types of plies $[90, \pm 55, 90]$.

Reinforcements, in glass fibers, are wound at the tubes extremities to hold them in experimental machines.

Fig. 1 Samples instrumentation.
Fiber and sollicitation references.

b- Experimental devices : (Fig. 1)

Tubes are tested under axial tractional, torsional and combined loads. Each test is instrumented like the previous description.

c- Uniaxial sollicitations :

Two types of tests are realised in tractional and torsional loads.

- Monotonous loads :

All sorts of tubes are so tested to know the global behaviour.

On the UD tube, we can determine the modulus (E_x, G_{xy}), estimate the rupture stresses (Y, S), the non-linearity limits (NLL) (Y_{NLL}, S_{NLL}) and the first acoustic signal (A.E.).

- Progressive repeated loads (PRL): (Fig. 3a)

To limit errors on the material characteristics, PRL are realised on the elementary sheet : it consists to load and unload at rising stress values, at the same loading speed. So, the NLL and the modulus evolution are determined more accurately. According to this evolution, we identify damage laws in tractional and torsional axis.

The elastic characteristics, NLL and rupture stresses in the other axis (as in fiber direction) are defined on plates samples.

CALCULATION

To modelize and to estimate the behaviour of multidirectional tubes, we use the elastic model of orthotropic plates with Katchanov type damage law, based on the modulus evolution.

The calculation way is describe in Fig. 2. This calculation is based on the damage of reduced stiffness matrix for plane stress, given by the damaged modulus. We must do an iteration on the stresses in the fiber axis because of the relation between the damage law and these stresses. By this computation, we can know:

- the behaviour of damaged complexe structures,
- each ply behaviour in the laminate,
- the NLL of each ply, by the quadratic Tsai criterion.

RESULTS

a- Determination of the damage laws :

They are evaluated from the modulus evolution in PRL on the UD tube.

- Axial tractional loads :

No modulus evolution was mesured, certified by a very little difference between load and unload in PRL response and the elastic behaviour. So, nodamage law exists in the transverse fiber direction.

- Torsional load : (Fig. 3)

Fig. 3(a)PRL under torsional sollicitation

(b)Gxy evolution: $G_{xy} = G_{xy}^0 + 2.199 \tau_{xy} - 0.182 \tau_{xy}^2$

Fig. 2 Computation plan
(Symbols description at the end of the text)

The global behaviour of UD tube shows an anelasticity. In the PRL test, the behaviour is still elastic, until an hysteresis apparition in the stress-strain curve corresponding with the non-linearity, and the first acoustic signal. We chose this state as the first damage. In the following loads, the modulus evolution characterizes the damage until rupture.

Damage law type : $G_{xy} = G_{xy}^0(1-d^n)$.

First, we verify that the calculation of the monotonous torsional behaviour of UD tube, taking into account the shear damage law, correspond with the experimental curve.

No damage is introduced in traction fiber, because of the linear behaviour.

b- Calculation and experiments comparison :

This study is made on BD and MD tubes (Fig. 4 & 5).

For the BD tubes, the initial modulus evolution brings some approximation difficulties, specially in axial tractional load, explained by differences in hypotheses between computation and experiments :

- tubes are wound by criss-crossed fibers but the calculation is made on a stack of plies.

- the behaviour is calculated ply by ply but plies interactions are shifted.

The previsions are better on MD tubes, because the $\pm 55^\circ$ ply contribution, by its thinner thickness, is less important. The 90° ply maintains all the other plies. There is just an interfiber decohesion of this sheet.

Tsai quadratic criterion, chosen from previous results [1], make a good expectation of the NLL.

Under axial tractional as torsional loads, the $\pm 55^\circ$ layers fibers are sollicitated in traction on the fiber direction or perpendicularly to them, but not in shear stress, where the damage law is the most important. So, there are other damage factors like :

- plies interaction,

- the transverse direction damage, not evaluated on UD tube in axial tractional load before a 17 MPa stress, but really exists in $\pm 55^\circ$ ply over this stress. The associated parameter d is not determined. An interaction exists between the damage parameters (d is a d^n function).

Fig. 4 Experimental and calculated behaviour of UD, BD and MD tubes under axial tractional load.

Fig. 5 Experimental and calculated behaviour of UD, BD and MD tubes under torsional load.

In general, the behaviour expectation with a Katchanov damage law is good until a damage rate, then there is a localisation of the damage and a catastrophic evolution.

CALCULATION UNDER BIAXIAL LOADS

The non-linearity surfaces in axial tractional, torsional and internal pressure load are determined by Tsai criterion for the three types of tubes (Fig. 6 & 7).

The damage level for each tube depends on the sollicitation way. The NLL appears at the sollicitation way and non-linearity surface crossing.

For the multidirectional tubes, the global criterion results is an intersection of the criterion envelope for each ply (symbolized by hachured areas). This is already verified in uniaxial load. By comparison of the hachured areas, we can notice that the addition of a 90° ply reduces the NLL in tractional-torsional load, but consolidates them in internal pressure.

Fig. 6 Tsai criterion surfaces for each ply of BD tube in torsional axial and circonferencial tractional axis.

Fig. 7 Tsai criterion surfaces for each ply of MD tube in torsional axial and circonferecial tractional axis

CONCLUSION

This simple model, composed by plate laminate theory, in addition with modulus damage laws, can well estimate the structure behaviour until the non-linearity limits.

After these limits, the damage prevision in BD tubes would be improved by a better method to mesure the transverse damage. So, we could extend this calculation application to BD and MD damage, until the rupture.

From the non-linearity surfaces, we can know how to load the structures to avoid the damage and to optimise the winding angle according to the sollicitation directions.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

- $E_x, E_y, G_{xy}, \nu_{xy}$: } elastics modulus and major Poisson's ratio in ply
 $E_1, E_2, G_{12}, \nu_{12}$: } and laminate reference.
 d, d', d'' : damage parameters in x, y axis and xy plane.
 $[J]$: coordinate transformation matrix for each ply.
 $[Q]$: reduced stiffness matrix for plane stress.
 $[A^*]$: in-plane stiffness matrix.
 ϵ : strain components.
 σ : stress components.
 Non- linearity limits (NLL):
 X_{NLL}, X'_{NLL} : longitudinal tensile and compressive strenght of a ply along the x-axis
 Y_{NLL}, Y'_{NLL} : transverse tensile and compressive strenght of a ply along the y-axis
 S_{NLL} : shear strenght in the xy-plane of a ply.
 $(-^o$: intact, $-^d$: damage).

REFERENCES

1. P. Joguet, C.Cazeneuve, J.C. Maile & C. Oytana, "Etude du comportement de tubes bobinés Kevlar/epoxy et carbone/epoxy sous sollicitations uniaxiales", J.N.C.6 Paris 1988, p. 539-552.
2. P. Ladeveze, "Sur la mécanique de l'endommagement des composites", J.N.C.5 Paris 1986, p. 667-683.
3. S.W. Tsai, "Introduction to composite materials", Techno. publishing A.G., 1980.